

ASSESSMENT OF LIVELIHOOD DIVERSIFICATION AMONG FARMING HOUSEHOLD IN KWALI AREA COUNCIL, FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The broad objective of the study was to assess livelihood diversification among farming households in Kwali Area Council, FCT, Nigeria. A three-stage sampling technique was used to select the sample size. A structured questionnaire was administered to 86 sampled households in the study area. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics, the Shannon diversification index, and the Tobit regression model. The results showed that an average farm household head was 47 years old, most (61.2%) of the farming household heads were male, the majority (62.4%) of the farming household heads were married, a higher percentage (35.3%) of farming household heads had no formal education, the average household size was 7 persons, and most (76%) of the farming household had a farm size between 0.1 and 2.5 hectares with a mean of 0.8 hectares. The result further revealed that 52.94% of the farming households were not involved in income diversification while about 21.18%, diversified their source of livelihood beyond three sources. Furthermore, the result revealed that the increase in livelihood diversification was influenced by household size and extension visits. This study concludes that crop production enterprise is the major strategy employed by the farming households in the study area. This study recommends that widespread awareness of the importance of formal education be made available to enhance farming households' level of diversification in the study area.

Keywords: Livelihood Diversification, Poverty Reduction, Living Standard and Income

INTRODUCTION

Over two-thirds of the less privileged people globally reside in rural areas and are involved in subsistence farming or small-scale agriculture (Bashiru, Dumayiri, and Kuwornu, 2014). In the emerging world, the ability of the agricultural sector to cater for the comfort and well-being of the people involved in agriculture is on the decline due to the massively increasing population growth with small farm sizes and the effect of urbanisation (Onunka and Olumba, 2023). The situation is not as different in Nigeria as the agricultural sector is currently considered and branded as

having a feeble and ineffective system of production, putrefied infrastructure, as well as being plagued with different risks and uncertainties. Therefore, rural family units are now forced to come up with new different strategies and new schemes to be able to muddle through and survive the challenge of agriculture and its different production systems through livelihood diversification (Abdulrahman, Abudlazeed, Binuyo, David, and Yusuf, 2016). Akanbi (2016) stated that one of the most prominent characteristics of farming households is livelihood diversification, which is often referred to as

occupational widening. It is described as the process by which farming households improve their quality of life and earn a livelihood by developing a different range of activities and social support skills (Akinyemi, Olayinka, Junaidu, Ekpa, Bodaga, and Ibrahim, 2021). Diversification plays a key part in the socio-economic life of the farming household and there is a need to analyse livelihood as it becomes absolutely important and serves as a defense of the poor and helpless household from economic, and environmental hazards and economic fluctuation, which spell danger and chaos for household income and affect consumption flow, which means the household would have to cut down on their cost of living (Akinyemi et al., 2021).

Despite the importance of diversification, farming households are confronted with numerous challenges because they only engage in farming as their sole source of livelihood, thereby limiting and reducing their income generation, which further affects the well-being of the entire farming household. The dependence on one source of livelihood has been the primary reason for the rise in poverty among many farming households. Many farming households are finding it very difficult to diversify their sources of livelihood owing to the fact that there has been a gap in knowledge. Many farmers are not aware or informed of the financial benefits and advantages of diversifying their means of livelihood and, as such, are left with the choice of practicing just farming as their sole source of livelihood (Stephen and Lenihan, 2010).

The main objective of this study was to assess the livelihood diversification among farming households in Kwali Area Council, FCT, Nigeria, while the specific objectives were to: examine the socioeconomic characteristics of farming households; identify the types of livelihood diversification among farming households; determine the level of livelihood diversification among farming households; and evaluate the factors influencing livelihood diversification among farming households in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area

The study was conducted in the Kwali Area Council of Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Nigeria. Kwali occupies 1,206 square Kilometers of land, or around 0.5% of the nation's total land area, and is situated between latitudes 4° 9' North and longitudes 7° 8' East of the equator. It has an average monthly temperature range of 23°C to 34°C, an annual rainfall range of 1100mm to 1600mm, and a derived savanna vegetation zone with short grasses, shrubs, and trees. According to the 2006 National Population Commission (NPC), 778,567 people were living in the Kwali Area Council. The majority of Kwali's indigenous people are subsistence farmers who grow yam, maize, guinea corn, beans, and millet. The locals and Bassa people also engage in a lot of fishing. In addition to farming, woodworking and crafts were and continue to be important professions for the locals, particularly the Gbagyis.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

A three-stage sampling technique was used for this study. Kwali Area Council was purposefully selected due to its preponderance of farming households in this area at the first stage. The second stage involved a random selection of six wards out of the ten wards in the Area Council. The selected wards were: Ashara, Kilamkwa, Kwali, Pai, Wako, and Yangoji. Finally, from a sample frame of 110 farming households, 86 were randomly selected as the sample size guided by the Yamane (1967) formula for the study. It is specified as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = 86 \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

n= Sample Size (Units)

N= Sample Frame (Units)

e² = Level of Precision (5%)

3.3: Method of Data Collection

The data used for this study consists mainly of

primary data. The primary data were obtained through the use of a semi-structured questionnaire. The semi-questionnaire was used to collect information on the socioeconomic characteristics, sources of income, the variety of crops they grew and animals reared, different types of livelihoods, diverse livelihoods, and factors influencing diversification in the study area.

Method of Data Collection

The analytical tools that were used in this study to achieve the stated objectives are:

- i. Descriptive Statistics
- ii. Shannon Diversification Index
- iii. Tobit Regression Analysis

Descriptive Analysis

The relevant instruments under this statistic include ratio, percentage, frequency distribution, measures of central distribution, and measures of dispersion. This was used to achieve specific objectives (i) and (ii), examine the socioeconomic characteristics of farming households, and identify the types of livelihood diversification among farming households in the study area.

Shannon Diversification Index

The Shannon index tool is an informational tool used to determine the level of diversification of the livelihood of farmers.

The equation for Shannon index is stated thus:

$$H = -\sum_{i=1}^S pi(\ln pi) \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

H=The Shannon diversity index

Pi = Fraction of the Entire Population Made up of Livelihood I, that is pi is the Proportion (n/N) of Farmers of One Particular Livelihood Found (n) Divided by the Total Number of Farmers Found (N)

S = Numbers of Livelihood Encountered

ln = Natural Logarithm

\sum = Sum from Livelihoods 1 to Farmers (S)

This was used to achieve a specific objective

(iii), determine the level of livelihood diversification among farming households in the study area.

Tobit Regression Analysis

Tobit regression was used to reveal the factors that prompted the diversification of livelihoods. According to Lamichhane, Sharma, and Adhikari (2018), the Tobit regression model is represented as follows:

$$Y_i = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_i + e \quad (3.3)$$

Where;

Y_i = the livelihood diversification index

X_i = the explanatory variables of the ith respondents

β = the coefficients of the explanatory variables

e_i = is the constant variance

The general Tobit regression model used in this study is expressed in its explicit form as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + \beta_9 X_9 + \beta_{10} X_{10} + e \quad (3.4)$$

Where:

Y = Livelihood Diversification Index

X_1 = Gender (male=1, female=0)

X_2 = Marital Status (married=1, otherwise=0)

X_3 = Age (years)

X_4 = Education (years)

X_5 = Household Size (numbers)

X_6 = Farm Size (hectares)

X_7 = Farming Experience (years)

X_8 = Membership of Cooperative (member=1, non-member=0)

X_9 = Period of Membership (year)

X_{10} = Extension Visit (numbers)

$\beta_1 - \beta_{10}$ = Regression coefficient or parameters

β_0 = Intercept

e_i = Error term

Tobit regression was used to achieve a specific objective (iv), investigate the factors influencing livelihood diversification among farming households in the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Farming Households in the Study Area

The respondents' socioeconomic characteristics are shown in Table 1. The findings show that 62.79% of them were male and 37.20% of the household heads were female. This suggests that the research area's respondents were mostly male-headed families. Furthermore, in Nigerian agricultural homes, which have a paternalistic mentality, men predominate as household leaders. As such, they have the responsibility of providing for the family's well-being. This finding is consistent with Omotayo's (2016) research in Ekiti State on the economic relationship between household poverty and rural off-farm income, which likewise found a higher proportion of farming families led by men in the study region. Also, 40.69% of the respondents were between the ages of 37 and 49, while around 30.23% were between the ages of 50 and 62, 18.60% were between the ages of 24 and 36, and 10.64% were between the ages of 63 and 75. The average age of the respondents was 47. The majority of respondents were relatively young and could afford to engage in different livelihood strategies and activities targeted at improving welfare, according to Amurtaya, Abudu, Adewuyi and Monsola (2021). In addition, 62.79% of respondents were married, 15.11% had lost a spouse, 12.9% were single, and 9.30% had divorced. This result conforms to the findings of Abiodun, Adewale, and Ojo (2019) who found out that the majority of marital status were married in Ondo State, Nigeria. The result of the household size of the respondents shows that between 1-7 members had 65.11%, 8-15 members had 32.55%, and 16-21 had 2.32% with a mean household size of 7. This result is consistent with the findings of Ahmed (2012), who noted that larger family sizes might increase the amount of labour needed for various agricultural tasks, including planting, weeding, harvesting, and clearing. Table 1 further reveals that 36.04%

had no formal education, 22.09% had primary school education, 16.27% attended tertiary education, 12.79% had quar'anic education while 10.46% had secondary school education and 2.32% had adult education. This means a significant percentage of the respondents had no formal education. This is in agreement with Ambali, Idowu and Onasanya (2014) who reported that uneducated farming household heads might not be risk-takers in diversifying their income due to the fear of the outcome. About 76.74% of the respondents had between 0.1- 2.5 hectares of farmland, 11% had between 2.6 – 4.5 hectares of land and another 11% had between 4.6 - 6.5 hectares of land for farming with an average farm size of about 0.8 hectares. This implies that the respondents were small-scale farmers in the study area. This result is in agreement with the finding of Lanjouw and Lanjouw (2001) who in their findings found that most empirical studies of African agriculture found no significant economies of scale beyond a very small farm size. This led most farmers to seek for alternative in non-farm activities. In addition, 77.90% had farming experience of between 3-15 years, while 22.09% had farming experience of between 16-35 years. The mean year of farming experience was 12. This is in concord with the findings of Oluwatusin and Sekumade (2016) who expounded that at 12 years of farming, household heads are well experienced in farming and can easily diversify their income activity. Furthermore, from Table 1 we found that 73.25% of the respondents were not members of a corporative while 26.74% were members of an agricultural corporative. This means that most of the farmers in the study area did not belong to agricultural corporative and as such did not have access to information that could assist in increasing their income. This is in line with Oluwatusin and Sekumade (2016) who stated that one of the means to tackle challenges such as access to credit, lack of information about the production process, and inadequate land is via corporative association.

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Farming Households in the Study Area

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
Gender	Male	54	62.79	
	Female	32	37.20	
Age	24 - 36	16	18.60	
	37 - 49	35	40.69	
	50 - 62	26	30.23	47
	63 - 75	9	10.46	
Marital Status	Married	54	62.79	
	Single	11	12.79	
	Divorced	8	9.30	
	Widow	13	15.11	
Household Size	1 - 7	56	65.11	
	8 - 15	28	32.55	
	16 - 21	2	2.32	7
Level of Education	No Formal Education	31	36.04	
	Primary Education	19	22.09	
	Secondary Education	9	10.46	
	Tertiary Education	14	16.27	
	Qur'anic Education	11	12.79	
	Adult Education	2	2.32	
Farm Size	0.1 - 2.5	66	76.74	
	2.6 - 4.5	10	11.62	
	4.6 - 6.5	10	11.62	0.8
Farming Experience	3 - 15	67	77.90	
	16 - 35	19	22.09	12
Member of Cooperative	Yes	23	26.74	
	No	63	73.25	

Source: Computed from field data, 2024

Distribution of Types of Livelihood Diversification among Farming Households in the Study Area

Table 2 shows the combination of livelihood diversification engaged in by the farming household in the study area. The combination involves farming and non-farming activities. The result shows that 51.16% were engaged in crop production only, 33.72% were engaged in both crop and animal production and 15.12% were involved in animal production only.

Furthermore, 59.30% were involved in civil service and private salaried earners, 17.44% were involved in the transport business, 8.13% were involved in tailoring, 6.97% were engaged in trading, 4.65% were involved in motor mechanic and 3.48% were involved in barbing or plaiting. This result agrees with the findings of Oyewole, Adepoju and Akintola (2015) who reported that crop production is the major source of income for most farming households in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Types of Livelihood Diversification among Farming Households in the Study Area

Livelihood Activities	Frequency	Percentage
Farm Activities		
Crop Production Only	44	51.16
Animal Production Only	13	15.12
Both Crop and Animal Production	29	33.72
Non-Farm Activities		
Civil Service and Private Salaried	51	59.30
Transport Business	15	17.44
Trading	6	6.97
Motor Mechanic	4	4.65
Tailoring	7	8.13
Barbing/Plaiting	3	3.48

Source: Computed from field data, 2024

Table 3: Level of Livelihood Diversification among Farming Households in the Study Area

Table 3 shows the level of livelihood diversification among farming households in the study area. The result shows that 53.48% of farming households had a low diversification index, i.e., they were diversified marginally or did not diversify. About 25.58% of the respondents diversified moderately, meaning they had at least two sources of income, while

20.93% had a high diversification index. Meaning that they had diversified their source of livelihood beyond two sources of income. This result disagrees with the findings of Akinyemi, Olayinka, Junaidu, Ekpa, Bodaga, and Ibrahim (2021), who reported that only a small number of farming households are engaged in one agricultural activity or venture.

Table 3: Level of Livelihood Diversification among Farming Households in the Study Area

Diversification Index	Frequency	Percentage	Level of Diversification
0 – 0.035	46	53.48	Low Diversification
0.036 – 0.06	22	25.58	Moderate Diversification
0.061 – 0.10	18	20.93	High Diversification
Total	86	100	

Source: Computed from field data, 2024

Tobit Regression Analysis of Livelihood Diversification among Farming Households in the Study Area

The results in Table 4 reveal that household size was significant at the 5% probability level. This implies that an increase in household size increases the possibility of diversifying income sources. In addition, the extension visit was

positively significant at the 1% probability level. This means that an increase in the services rendered by the extension agent leads to an increase in livelihood diversification. This result conforms to Oluwatusin and Sekumade (2016), whose study revealed that access to extension agents provides information that encourages livelihood diversification.

Table 4: Tobit Regression Analysis for the Factors Influencing Livelihood Diversification among Farming Households in the Study Area

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	z-value	p > (z)
Gender	.0340224	.1446519	0.24	0.814
Marital Status	-.0374669	.0677075	-0.55	0.580
Age	.0038592	.0084989	0.45	0.650
Level of Education	.0670188	.0481577	1.39	0.164
Household Size	.0588048**	.0231798	2.54	0.011
Farm size	.0149379	.1095423	0.14	0.892
Farming Experience	-.0127042	.012458	-1.02	0.308
Membership of Corporative	.1262937	.3132387	0.40	0.687
Period of Membership	.0639869	.0560972	1.14	0.254
Extension Visit	.8286004*	.1863406	4.45	0.000
Constant	.8286004	.4403749	1.88	0.060
Log Likelihood	-77.321639			
Wald Chi ² (10)	65.71			
Prob > Chi ²	0.0000			
Livelihood Diversification	.3611202	.0553933		

Source: Computed from field data, 2024

***Significant at 1%, ** Significant at 5% Probability Levels**

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study assessed the livelihood diversification among farming households in Kwali Area Council, Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. The study shows that the farming household derived income from farming, where crop production enterprise is the leading source of income followed by both crop and animal enterprises. It can therefore be concluded that crop production enterprise is the major strategy employed by the farming household in the study area. The farming

household's level of livelihood diversification is low. Nonetheless, a few of them have a medium and a high level of livelihood diversification. The major factors that influence their level of livelihood diversification are household size and extension visits. This study recommends that a widespread awareness of the importance of formal education should be made to enhance farming household's level of diversification in the study area

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